

DRYING AND CLEANING COTTON RAW MATERIALS**Ulug'murodov Elshod Abdusalim o'g'li**

Student Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnics at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and agricultural Mechanization Engineers"

ulugmurodovelshod2001@mail.ru

Sayfullayev Sirojjon Ikrom o'g'li

Student Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnics at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and agricultural Mechanization Engineers"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10554196>

Annotation. A new unit was developed, where the drying and cleaning of cotton raw materials was carried out simultaneously. In the new block, the effectiveness of the convective drying method is increased by increasing the speed at which cotton is moved in the countercurrent flow of the drying agent.

Keywords: Raw cotton, humidity, drying, temperature, drying barbecue, drying and cleaning of cotton, small weeds.

Abstract. A new unit has been developed in which the drying and cleaning of raw cotton is carried out simultaneously. The efficiency of the convective drying method in the new block is increased by increasing the speed of movement of the cotton raw material in the countercurrent of the drying agent.

Keywords: Raw cotton, moisture, drying, temperature, drying drum, cotton drying and cleaning, fine weeds.

ACCESS

The drying of cotton raw materials at the forefront of the continuous process of its processing is aimed at reducing the humidity of cotton raw materials to the values recommended in technological regulations, resulting in the reliable and efficient operation of subsequent cleaning equipment. . Therefore, drying cotton is one of the main and necessary operations of the technological process. There are many known ways to dry cotton materials. For drying raw cotton, a convective method is currently used mainly, in which crude cotton is heated by atmospheric air or its mixture combustion products in a natural gas or other fuel heat generator. The convective method is used in both local and foreign dryers of cotton. [1]

Barbecue dryers of type 2SB-10, which are currently used in cotton plants, have serious disadvantages. The heat consumption of the dryer for drying direct cotton raw materials is only 35-40%, while the remaining heat is mainly released into the atmosphere for heating the dryer and with the spent dryer,

polluting the environment. In this case, it is almost impossible to re-turn the drying tool due to pollution and moisture.

The greatest heat loss in dryers of 2SB-10 occurs with a 40-45% spent drying agent. To reduce these losses, several attempts have been made to re-convert the spent dryer through aerator to pump into the gas canal, which has led to a deterioration in the technological parameters of drying and cleaning the cotton. This is due to the fact that the dried dryer contains moisture, small residues, dust and loose fibers released from cotton beets. An attempt to pre-clean the used dryer also failed. In barbecue dryers, the drying time is 5-8 minutes, thanks to which not only fiber, but also seeds are dried, which is not desirable when the dryer is introduced into the continuous process of processing cotton. Barbarecs have up to 1.5 tons of cotton beans at a time, which complicates the elimination of fires. These dryers are morally and physically obsolete. Currently, technology is successfully used in the United States, including pre-softening of raw cotton, then cleaning it from fine and coarse litter in dryers that reproduce and alternately dry twice in a row. This technology will mutually enhance drying and cleaning, as softened and cleaned cotton will be dried more efficiently, and heated cotton will be cleaned more efficiently. When cotton dryers dry up to 15% of the humidity of varieties I, II and III in grades 1 and 2, they must ensure reliable operation with a capacity of up to 10 tons. When the consumed temperature of 5.6 m³/sec and its temperature is 130-150 °C, the extraction of moisture is 3-5%. [2,3,4]

STUDY FINDINGS

As shown in the diagram (Figure 1), four horizontal hollow trays with holes 17 are installed in the corpse of the equipment for pumping the dryer into the drying chamber 16. Each hollow patch has holes for the delivery and removal of the dryer, which are combined with holes on the side of the corpse. Valve 2 was installed in the equipment corps, an SS-15A separator was installed on it 1. Under feed valves 3, during four loosening barbarecs, there are 5 mounted with holes at the base of 4 of the horizontal line, and between them are prone and attached vessels of 6 and 7. In addition, the first five drums on the block body contain five barbarecs of the line with five-hole lace 13 under 13. Beneath the cotton cotton smear and the last drum are formed a drop hole (15). There are 8 longitudinal grass points under 5steshion nets and 6, 7 trays, their grooves are located next to the transverse tube. Drilling device No. 10, on top of which a hole of up to 11 is made to connect the aspiration pipe on the side of the corpse. As you can see from the form. 2, delivery of the drying tool from the IICH-1.9 1 heat

generator to the DN-11.2 4 smoke outlet is carried out through 3-door pipeline 2. The pipe line, which comes out of the drying agent's re-circulation system, includes 5. Tubes 6 and 4 with four network pipes attached to four hollow trays (7) from holes next to the corpse, equipped with a door up to 11, pipes that connect hollow trays 7 to pipeline 2 through the network 9.

Figure 1. Drying and Cleaning Device Figure 2. Delivery and re-rotation of the dryer in a drying and cleaning device

The system for removing the use of dryer and dryer corps aspiration includes a pipeline line 13, equipped with a door 14 and connected to 15 assimilation holes of the ventilator, connected to the hole in the corpse of Block 8.

of which 17 tsikh and the pipeline are connected through 16. [5]

The work of the drying and cleaning device is carried out as follows (Figure 1). By feeding the valves, the first punching drum from 2nd tomato cotton is given 4, it is emptied and transported along the mesh 5 with holes and then makes it to the first level in the direction of the 6th laganda. 19 chamber along the road, followed by cotton flow - the raw material moves upwards, falls on top of the second drurah 4. After that, the above-mentioned process is repeated.

From the last, fourth drudane, The lower first drum along the cotton cotton falls to 13, then all the other drums of the prone line that transport the cottoncomble along the perforated nets are down to 13, and then part 13 of the prone line from which the Hole Net does not exist from the last drum, and up to 15 through the drop hole through the drop hole of cotton cotton. Up to 5 of the horizontal line are placed in 8 bunkers with alien substances released through a piercing mesh. 9, lowers them into the cross horn 10, and 14 separated alien substances through the peripheral nets immediately descend into the transverse cord 12 along the bending tube 10, which takes them down from the body.

When the drying tool is delivered from the heat generator, approximately 50% of its volume is absorbed into the camera through the cavity lagans 16 and their hole holes are 17 through the chamber, i.e. the block body, then the bars with 5 and 14 holes are poured into the zone with waste of 9 and 10 release cords, from which it is absorbed by 11 openings. The device performs convective and contact drying and drying with infrared light. During the device's operation, all its working organs, components and internal surfaces are heated by a drying tool formed in a heat generator and are hit by smoke waste through hollow trays into the equipment chamber, and there are also empty trays. They are additionally heated by tubular electric heaters (TEN), while moving along the bars with holes, along the walls and along prone trays, the cotton beetle is heated, that is, through contact drying. The resulting embryo was allowed to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it implanted. [2,3,4]

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the department, cotton is transferred simultaneously to communications and convective drying methods, which increases its overall efficiency and covers the relatively short life span of cotton due to these drying methods.

References:

1. Borodin P.N. Study and Testing of the Complex of Technological Equipment Produced by the People's Republic of China AO Paxtasanoat ilmiy markazi, Tashkent, 2011. 85 p. (in Russian).
2. Tojiev, R J. (2019) "DRYING GLASS FEED STOCK IN DRUM DRIER FOR MANUFACTURING GLASS PRODUCTS," Scientific-technical journal: Vol. 22: Iss. 3, Article 21. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/ferpi/vol22/iss3/21>
3. Abdukodirov N., Okyulov K. DRUM DRYER DESIGN IMPROVEMENT: https://a78cf8ac-3ef5-4670-8fcd-a900ec94fdfb.filesusr.com/ugd/b06fdc_08e83b3119384163a0da8c5e27d97871.pdf?index=true
4. Abduqodirov son of Nurzod Shavkatjon, construction of a regression model for drying and cleaning raw cotton (pp.687-693) <http://scientificprogress.uz/storage/app/media/2-1.%20114.%20687-693.pdf>
5. "Compressor wallaridas salbium titrashlarnis bartaraf vertebrate kimyovy termikishlov beryb cementitishing methology va afzalillari", slxi International Scientific and Practical Conference of Halkaro Technics Journals. 01.04.2020 й. 312-317 бет. <https://www.internauka.org/authors/okyulov-kamoldin-rahmat-ugli>